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DRONE FOR SPRAYING HERBICIDE AND PESTICIDE

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IMPLEMENTATION OF DRONE FOR SPRAYING HERBICIDE AND PESTICIDE

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ABSTRACT

This project report describes an experimental test campaign while using an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and measuring the obtained UAV positions during different flight tasks and in different operative conditions. This paper describes and analyses the measurements of the flight trajectory of the UAV that was performed with the use of a robotic total station (RTS), as compared to the design data and the data recorded in the internal memory of the UAV. Five different test tasks have been conducted. The obtained results have allowed for the assessment of the correctness of task performance as compared to the design and to determine the flying accuracy of the entire UAV set. The proposed set of tasks can be successfully utilized to control the correctness of operation of various types of UAVs and it may be implemented as a universal test to verify the algorithms optimizing take and landings, test flights of the objects, as well as flight planning in various terrain and weather conditions, which will increase the safety of the flights while using UAVs. Chapter two states and describe agricultural drone as form for spraying water and pesticides and how spraying systems help the efficiency of agricultural drones and, how to research on the spraying system of drones for sufficient usage. In this project report a new nozzle with a feedback channel is proposed for agricultural drones. The proposed nozzle was manufactured through 3D printing, and its performance was compared with that of the nozzle used in commercial agricultural drones. It also explains how Images taken with a high-speed camera were digitally processed, and how to track the area and location of spray particles. The spraying characteristics were evaluated based on the size and uniformity of the droplets obtained from the images. The Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) was implemented and construct the variable-rate spraying technology, as the development direction of aviation for plant protection in the future, has been developed rapidly in recent years. In the actual agricultural production, the severity of plant diseases and insect pests varies in different locations. In order to reduce the waste of pesticides, pesticides should be applied according to the severity of pests, insects and weeds.

INTRODUCTION

The Drone use for spraying Herbicide and pesticide refers to an **agricultural drone** used in optimizing agricultural operations, increase crop production, and monitor crop growth. With the aid of constructing and implementing such component like: Sensors and digital imaging that helps farmers to rich a picture of a far places of their fields. Using an agriculture drone and gathering information from it may prove useful in improving crop yields and farm efficiency.

Fig. 1: An agricultural drone while spraying at Farm land

The aerial view provided by a drone can reveal many issues such as irrigation problems, soil variation, and pest and fungal infestations. Multispectral images show a near-infrared view as well as a visual spectrum view. The combination shows the farmer, the differences between healthy and unhealthy plants, a difference that human eye cannot be able detect it clearly. Thus, these views can assist in assessing crop growth and production. Crops can be surveyed at any time using agricultural drones, allowing for rapid identification of problems.

In this era of modern technologies, the structure of rural labor force throughout the whole World has changed drastically. It has increased the contradiction regarding the demand and Lack of rural labor force available therefore agricultural equipment with higher efficiency Is sought after in order to serve for the agricultural production. Besides that, crop diseases and pests are major factors affecting the quality and yield of crops. Chemical pesticides will be the main solution in order to control and prevent this from happening.

The selection of the equipment to be used is a critical factor for chemical pest control. In Country like Nigeria, there are More than 88% of manually operated sprayers that includes manual air-pressure or electric Knapsack sprayer and knapsack mist-blower sprayer. The quality of the spraying process mainly depends on the skill of the sprayers. 2010, the market of drones is estimated to be around 4.9 billion USD. Based on Analytical data, business services that are using drones have been valued to grow to Approximately 127 billion USD. The agricultural industry has embraced drone technology where these advanced tools are being used to modernize the traditional. Agricultural drones are transforming the way farming is being carried out. Nowadays, while the demand is set to grow, farmers must consider a variety of complex factors which will impact the success of their agriculture businesses or farms ranging from the water Access to soil quality, rainfall patterns, temperature, changing climate, wind, the presence of Weeds and insects. Farmers must continue to innovate in order to improve and maintain the Productivity to meet the demands. Digital technologies have huge potentials to provide Farmers with all the required data to seize the opportunities for growth and meet these Challenges. Consequently, farmers are reaching out to agricultural drone technology in Order to help mitigate these problems. The demands of UAVs have increased and are used for a various type of missions.

Digital agriculture is defined as the use of digital technology to integrate agricultural Production from the paddock to the consumer. Digital agriculture also uses the most advanced and latest technologies which are integrated into one system to enable farmers and other

stakeholders within the agriculture value chain to improve production. The UAV can be piloted autonomously via flight control software or manually via transmitter. Advanced agricultural drones will allow farmers and the drone pilots that operate them to improve and increase the efficiency in certain aspects of the farming process. These aspects range from crop planting monitoring, crop spraying, livestock management and irrigation mapping. The digital technologies used can provide the agricultural industry with all the necessary information and tools to make more informed decisions. Agriculture Spraying drones are much bigger in size where they will have a larger and wider spraying Span. They can increase and improve the efficiency of spraying more area of land in a shorter duration compared to a knapsack sprayer. Moreover, the variable spray technology Used by the agricultural UAV can be applied on demand therefore it has definite potential and prospects. Once the drone technology is implemented, agriculture businesses and farms can save time and increase crop yields which will improve long-term success.

Background of Study

An Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV), commonly known as a drone, is an aircraft without a human pilot aboard. Essentially, a drone is a flying robot. UAVs are a component of an unmanned aircraft system (UAS); which include ground-based controller, and a system of Communications between the two. The flight of UAVs May operate with various degrees of autonomy: either under Remote control by a human operator or autonomously by onboard computers. An example of drone such as Quad copters, generally use two Pairs of identical fixed pitched propellers; two clockwise and two counter clockwise (CCW). These use independent

Variation of the speed of each rotor to achieve control. By changing the speed of each rotor it is possible to specifically generate a desired total thrust; to locate for the center of Thrust both laterally and longitudinally; and to create a desired total torque, or turning force.

Crop spraying with the unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) Sprayer does not need a runway; they can take off and land vertically. Flying at low altitude of several meters, the Crop-spraying can be controlled in any the sight of distance Range. They are suitable for all kinds of complex terrain, Crops and plantations of varying heights. Precise and Accurate crop spraying which ensures the best coverage and Application of fertilizers or pesticides on lands. Aerial Application or what was formerly referred to as crop dusting, Involves spraying crops with crop protection products from an agricultural aircraft. Until recently user needed a specialized agricultural aircraft to perform these operations. The Aerial Application Agricultural Spray Combines new pumps and spray heads designed to be more reliable. The technology and the results obtained by it leave No question that low and ultra-low volume. Spraying is a viable alternative in today's environmentally aware world. Better results are achieved with fewer chemicals. Some of The benefits of crop spraying with a UAV Sprayers include a Significant reduction in application cost by utilizing an UAV Aircraft and a notable improvement in coverage and control Through consistent application of the best suited droplet size For better penetration of crop canopy, decreased drift Potential and evaporation, and greater adherence of chemical To the leaves. The spray system was designed to promote economically and ecologically sound spray methods that are the future of agricultural aviation.

Agricultural unmanned helicopters and multi-rotors can take off vertically which effectively lowers the

operation Difficulty and the risks. Flying at low altitude of several Meters, the spraying effect can be controlled in the active Area. It is suitable for all kinds of complex terrain farmlands and the crops and woods of different heights. The spraying Operation skills of agriculture UAV Sprayer can be mastered via simple training. Environment-Friendly – The dosage of Pesticide is reduced, so it can minimize the pollution of Pesticide to the environment and crops. It is not harmful to the operator in the distances when dusting, and the labor Intensity is reduced dramatically. Precision agriculture, also called precision Farming, refers to the way farmers manage crops

To ensure efficiency of inputs such as water and Fertilizer, and to maximize productivity, quality, and yield. The term also involves minimizing Pests, unwanted flooding, and disease. Drones allow farmers to constantly monitor crop and livestock conditions by air to quickly find Problems that would not become apparent in Ground-level spot checks. For example, a farmer Might find through time-lapse drone photography that part of his or her crop is not being properly Irrigated.

Agricultural or Farming Drones

Agricultural drone technology has been improving in the last few years, and the benefits of drones in agriculture are becoming more apparent to farmers. Drone applications in Agriculture range from mapping and surveying to Crop-dusting and spraying.

Drone applications in agriculture are on the rise. Reuters On the surface, agricultural drones are no Different than other types of drones. The Application of the UAV simply changes to fit the Needs of the farmer. There are, however, several Drones specifically made for agricultural use. The process of using a drone to map or

survey Crops is a relatively straightforward one. Many Newer agricultural drone models come equipped with flight planning software that allows the user to draw around the area he or she needs to cover to use as for Map/Survey. Then, the software makes an automated Flight path and, in some cases, even prepares the Camera shots.

As the drone flies, it automatically takes pictures Using onboard sensors and the built-in camera and uses GPS to determine when to take each Shot. But if your drone does not have these Automatic features, then one person needs to fly the drone while the other takes the photos. **capable of spraying crops** with far more precision Than a traditional tractor Drones in action In 2015, the Federal Aviation Administration Approved the Yamaha RMAX as the first drone Weighing more than 55 pounds to carry tanks of Fertilizers and pesticides in order to spray crops. Drones such as this are capable of spraying crops with far more precision than a traditional Tractor. This helps reduce costs and potential Pesticide exposure to workers who would have needed to spray those crops manually.

Drones have revolutionized agriculture by Offering farmers major cost savings, enhanced Efficiency, and more profitability as its Benefits in the field of Agriculture. By quickly surveying vast stretches of farmland, drones can detect the property, report on crop health, improve Spraying accuracy, and monitor livestock and Irrigation systems, and more. The ability to collect and analyze this data in real

Time has tangible outcomes for farmers such as Better crop yield; fewer resources expended on Weeds and herbicides, and overall improved Management decisions.

Insider Intelligence expects spending on the Overall drone market to surpass \$12 billion by 2021. But what about the agricultural drone Market specifically?

Global Market Insights forecasts that the Agricultural drone market size will exceed \$1 Billion and 200,000 units shipped by 2024. GMI attributes the growth through 2024 to increasing Awareness of the pros and cons of drones in Agriculture among farmers. The company also claims that technological Advancements in farming techniques will push Demand during the forecast period. Increased Automation stemming from a lack of skilled Resources and a labor crisis will also bolster Agricultural drone demand. Finally, GMI expects Government programs in this sector to permit Operations of various sizes to help make farming Processes more efficient.

Statement of Problem

Pests and diseases of crops are a major factor affecting the yield and quality of crops, and chemical Pesticides are the main means for their prevention and control. The pesticide application method Currently used in Nigeria and other country is mainly based on uniform spraying. Therefore, the utilization rate of Pesticides and herbicides is still low. According to statistics, as of 2017, the pesticide utilization Rate in Nigeria and other country such as china was only 36.6%, which was lower than the level of 50% in developed countries. The Extensive use of pesticides directly endangers the ecological environment and human health. Therefore, Pesticide reduction and efficiency have been realized worldwide. In the field of plant protection, the Variable spray technology can be applied on demand. It has definite prospects and potentialities in improving the utilization rate of pesticides and reducing pesticide residues. Developed a field information processing

system. based on a Bedouin positioning embedded vehicle for variable sprayer. The system was able to complete the spray operation according to the generated job prescription map. However, the performance of field information processing system was not completely verified by the field testing. Used a geospatial prescription map prepared for olive trees, along with Real-Time Kinematic-Global Positioning System (RTK-GPS)-based position information to control the spray rate. This system only implements variable spray based on tree shape, and does not combine the degree of disease and pest with tree shape. Used a **variable-pressure spray system** that controls the flow rate with an electric control valve. The step responses of the five target flows were measured experimentally. The results showed that the rise time, peak time and overshoot of the nonlinear system have amplitude correlation. However, the way of regulating flow by an electronic control valve is only applicable to ground machinery. Compared with the high-speed flight of plant protection unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV), the response time of the electronic control valve has a greater impact on the system. Designation of a nonlinear variable spray system based on pressure regulation. By establishing the transfer function of the open-loop system, the nonlinear control of the variable spray system was realized. However, for the low volume spray of plant protection UAV, the droplet size and the effect of spraying operation will be affected by the pressure. Shahemabadi and Moayed proposed an algorithm to improve the Pulse width modulation (PWM) algorithm. By controlling the rising or falling state of the valve opening corresponding to the high and low pulse levels, an adjustment range of the flow rate from 0% to 100% can be realized according to the adjustment precision of 2.5%. The response time

by using pulse to adjust valve opening cannot meet the requirements of UAV high-speed flight.

At present, the precision variable spraying technology for ground plant protection machinery in Nigeria is developing more rapidly. However, the technology of agricultural aviation plant protection is still in its infancy, mainly because the plant protection UAV is faster than the ground plant protection machinery. UAV has the characteristics of high control precision and fast response speed to the variable spray system. In this study, a plant protection UAV variable spray system is designed based on the interpretation of the work prescription map. The system obtains prescription information for real-time location through graphic interpretation of plant protection UAV, and PWM-Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) control is used to adjust the spray volume quickly and accurately. The stability and feasibility of the system are verified by experiments, which provide a theoretical reference for the research of plant protection of UAV variable spray system and extend to the field of modern agricultural aviation for plant protection.

landmark report published by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) states that sustainable land management could be key to reversing the impact of climate change on land degradation – a significant consequence of human and agricultural activity and extreme weather conditions, in which the quality of land and soil is polluted or degraded. The report claims that this could provide “cost-effective, immediate and long-term benefits”. With this in mind, it is crucial that farms change how they operate to not only mitigate the effects of climate change, but to protect themselves against economic loss. The Rise of Precision Agriculture to balance feeding the planet with reducing global Emissions, ambitious plans has been put in place. The

U.K.’s National Farmers’ Union (NFU), for example, has outlined its goal of making British agriculture carbon neutral By 2040, with the introduction of a range of measures to Improve land management, increase farming efficiencies, And boost the wider bio economy. Although there is no Single answer to the problem, the NFU has advocated Working “smarter” to cut direct pollution from farming, by delivering the same value with fewer emissions. Precision agriculture practices, which can help farmers, make better informed decisions; have evolved significantly over recent years, with the global market now estimated to reach \$43.4 billion by 2025. While drones, which also known as Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), have not yet made it into The mainstream agriculture space, they are playing an Increasingly important role in precision farming, helping Agriculture professionals lead the way with sustainable Farming practices, while also protecting and increasing Profitability.

The use of global positioning system (GPS) technology, Together with geographic information system (GIS) tools, Form a large part of these precision agriculture practices Allowing fine-scale monitoring and mapping of yield and Crop parameter data within fields. These provide more Intense and efficient cultivation methods, which can help Farmers adjust fertilizer prescriptions or identify crop Diseases before they become widespread. With more data at their fingertips, farmers can make decisions based on Economic and environmental factors – for example, by Optimizing fertilizer treatment and applying only the right Amount at the right time, significant cost and environmental Savings can be made.

The Adoption of Drones The use of drones in the agriculture industry is steadily growing as part of an effective approach to sustainable Agricultural management that allows agronomists, Agricultural

engineers, and farmers to help streamline their Operations, using robust data analytics to gain effective Insights into their crops. Crop monitoring, for example, is Made easier by using drone data to accurately plan and Make ongoing improvements, such as the use of ditches And evolving fertilizer applications. Products can be accurately traced from farm to fork using GPS locations for every point in the journey, rather than more traditional time and labor-intensive data collection.

The technology has also proven Useful in gaining an extensive overview of plant emergence and population, as more accurate data can help with Replanting decisions, as well as thinning and pruning activity And the improvement of crop models. Crucially, the high-resolution nature of drone data can be used to assess the fertility of crops, allowing agricultural Professionals to more accurately apply fertilizer, reduce Wastage, and plan – and troubleshoot – irrigation systems. The technology can also be particularly effective following Natural disasters, such as a flood, to help farmers to assess Damage across terrains that may not be readily accessible on foot. Taking Drones Further the potential for UAVs in the improvement of sustainable Agriculture is huge. Already the agriculture drone market is predicted to be worth US\$32.4 billion – an indication that the industry is beginning to recognize the benefits over more traditional methods, such as ground mapping. Given the extensive terrain that requires surveying, drones Offer increased efficiency, allowing users to capture high- Resolution imagery more quickly than alternative methods. Particularly in these volatile market conditions, estimating Annual yield can help guide decision-making and manage Expectations. In addition, UAVs are now seen as a safer

Option for mapping difficult areas, such as uneven or Expansive fields, that can be hazardous for operators –

Particularly compared to terrestrial techniques, which must be carried out on-foot.

Where satellites and manned aircrafts have traditionally been used to monitor agriculture, UAVs are quickly Becoming recognized as a more accurate and cost-effective Replacement. Studies have shown that drone imagery provides a higher rate of accuracy and resolution – even on Cloudy days. While using traditional terrestrial approaches to collect data in challenging weather conditions could potentially delay projects for days, accurate crop health Assessments can be made throughout the year using UAVs.

Problems of Some Components.

Operator Exposure is reduced compared to handheld Application. Opponents talk about productivity and cost factors Compared to manned aerial application, spray drift, and rogue use. Before drone spraying becomes commonplace, two Important things need to happen. Federal laws need to be updated to accommodate the unique features of remotely piloted aircraft Systems (RPAS), as they're now called. Current laws make many assumptions unique to manned ships, and the process to correct that will require some Patience. A thorough review for US laws, and their Shortcomings, can be found here. Federal pesticide labels need to permit the use of Drones for application. As of August, 2021, Canadian Labels have no such registered use. There is no doubt that we need to prepare for a Future that includes spraying by drones. Features such As topography adjustment for height consistency and Autonomous swath control are already essentially standard, and the capabilities that improve control and safety will continue to develop. And yet I've been nervous about the prospect of Pesticide application with drones. My primary Concern is around – you guessed it

– spray drift. Because a drone payload is relatively small (about 5 To 25 L, depending on the model), application Volumes will need to be low to have any sort of Productivity. How low? For manned aircraft with a 200 to 600 gallon hopper, 2 to 4 US gpa (18 to 36 L/Ha) are the lowest commonplace volumes. The lower Volumes require a Medium spray quality (among the Finer sprays in modern boom spray practice) to Achieve the required coverage. It's a simple concept: the less water is used, the Smaller the droplets need to be to provide the Necessary droplet density on the target. Drift control with coarser sprays requires higher volumes, and true Droplet-size-based low-drift spraying can't really Happen at volumes less than, say 5 to 7 US gpa. At 2 to 4 US gpa, a drone would be able to do Perhaps 1 acre per load. While OK for spot spraying,

It represents a serious productivity constraint for Anything larger. There will be a push toward lower Volumes, perhaps 0.5 to 1 gpa (5 to 10 L/ha). The Only way these will provide sufficient coverage is with finer sprays, ASABE Fine to Very Fine, with expected Problematic effects on off-target movement and Evaporation. These fine droplets are also more prone to the aerodynamic eccentricities of aircraft. Vortices from the rotor can create unpredictable droplet Movement.

The current regulatory models for aerial drift Assessment in North America, AgDISP and AgDRIFT, Are not yet able to simulate drone application. But by Entering finer sprays into these models for their Conventional manned rotary wing aircraft, we can see that buffer zones will be higher. Much higher and that outcome will give pause to regulators. Failure to Control the movement of a spray is, and should be, a Problem.

Estimated Buffer Zones (calculated by AgDISP) for a reference Rotary wing spray aircraft, using three

pesticide toxicologies and two spray qualities. Furthermore, ultra-low volume (ULV) sprays can Change the efficacy of some products, and these will require new performance studies. At this time, Regulators are seeking information not just on spray Drift, but on product efficacy, operator and bystander Exposure, and crop residues.

Regulators are currently collecting spray drift and Efficacy data from drones. Since the drones available In today's market do not conform to a common Design standard like fixed or rotary winged manned Aircraft, each model may have its own characteristics And need its own study. Some will have rotary Atomizers, others will use hollow cone hydraulic Sprays. Some will have electrostatic charging, others May propose special adjuvants. Once data are assessed, there will likely be Restrictions in flight height, flight speed, wind speed, Spray quality, water volume, perhaps air temperature And relative humidity (or Delta T). This is not new to Spraying, as current labels already constrain use for both ground and aerial spray application, more so for Aerial.

The obvious question is how these proper application Practices can possibly be assured. Operators will need more than just regulatory approval to use a Drone; they will require proper training, similar to what A commercial aerial applicator now receives prior to Operating a business. Recall that our aerial applicators are governed by National organizations, the NAAA in the US and the CAAA in Canada. These organizations are in regular Contact with federal regulators to assure compliance.

They also help fund research into application efficacy and safety. They organize conferences in the off- Season and calibration clinics in the growing season At these, flow rates are confirmed and deposited Droplet size is

measured. Spray pattern uniformity is Assessed and corrected as necessary. Should drone applications be exempt from these Controls? I don't think that would be wise. Are we Ready to implement them? absolutely not. These requirements would change the drones' Economic model. And despite these precautions, a Drone may still leave the control of a pilot due to unforeseen technical or human events. In the US, Yamaha does not sell their drone Helicopters. Instead, they deploy their own teams to make the applications. This way, they have assurance that only trained and experienced pilots use the Technology. As the industry gears up for the first registrations, we See drone service companies take a leading role in Testing. Much is being learned via legal applications of liquid micronutrients, for example, or limited use of Pesticides under approved research permits.

Significance of The Project

In the last few years, several public and private research developers started investing a considerable Amount of resources for the construction of human-friendly unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) or 'Drones'. These devices immediately found a great deployment in the society opening an incredible Amount of new opportunities as useful tools to address a variety of societal challenges, including Agriculture and forest analysis, identifying property boundaries, surveying construction sites or Corridors for roads and railroads, stockpile volume calculations, flooding and coastal erosion Assessments, building information management, disaster planning and handling, surveys in remote or

undeveloped areas and the delivery of goods. The possibilities of digitalization and technology Development address societal challenges such as

making societal sectors and domains more ecosystems Friendly, efficient and competitive. This project will work to define societal challenges and ways to address those using applications of drone technology. The project will also study potential (unintended) consequences of such applications in terms of risks and ethical questions. Despite the enormous achievements, drones have sufficient control autonomy and capability to complete only part of these activities and the majority of the applications previously described still Rely on human supervision. This platform represents an important opportunity to develop and combine Cross-disciplinary research activities in several strategic fields. Having knowledge on drone technology development helps one to know some basic mode operation of machine device like: (robotics, AI, image processing), research application (e.g. Remote sensing and the study of cultural heritage) and applications in different societal sectors (e.g. Forestry, agriculture, energy, construction, rescue operations) to make them inform of each other in a Collaborative learning environment and create new synergies. We also aim to incorporate and integrate user views and perspectives to enable the development of knowledge and innovation Directed towards private companies as well as the public sector. The project is expected to result in an increased network of collaborating partners, interdisciplinary grants for research and demonstrable Applications for autonomous drone operations in the selected areas. Drones for addressing societal challenges is less due to high potential for use of drone data Within a variety of societal fields, however, currently there is a knowledge gap between technology Developers and stakeholders. The project aims at bridging this gap by creating an arena for knowledge Sharing and to identify needs and means for technology to address the societal challenges.

Communication and information exchange is a key tool in this process. The project will stimulate this Exchange across several sectors, and will also focus on a set of demonstration projects, initially four, and those that will act as models for future expansion:

Agriculture: based on ongoing collaboration with SLU the implementation of drone focus on the societal Need to make agriculture more efficient and sustainable (precision agriculture). A first focus is on technological development on the use of autonomous drone systems for optimized use of Pesticides and fertilizers.

Forestry: the implementation also focuses on the use of drones for identifying forest damage and needs for Management interventions. Thus, the methods should enable rapid and automatic Identification of damaged trees, but also of areas of protection, e.g. wetlands, rare tree species Etc.

Archaeology: the study also helps in focusing for cost-efficient and automatic detection and recording of new archaeological sites. The result of such work will provide important Indications on which areas need to be preserved from extent urban development.

Town planning and management: the project will explore rational use of this new technology for 3D-mapping and surveying of urban areas. The long-term aspects will include systems that provide a large degree of autonomy, not only in flying but also in the identification of the problem, the required action, and carrying out possible counter-Active measurements.

LITERATURE REVIEW

An agricultural drone or sprayer drone is an unmanned aerial vehicle used to help optimize agriculture operations, increase crop Production, and monitor crop growth. Sensors and digital imaging capabilities that

gives farmers a richer picture for their fields. Using an agriculture drone and gathering Information from it may prove useful in improving crop Yields and farm efficiency. An agricultural drone in a field performing the Task of crop spraying the aerial view provided by a drone can reveal many issues Such as irrigation problems, soil variation, and pest and Fungal infestations. Multispectral images show a near- Infrared view as well as a visual spectrum view. The Combination shows the farmer the differences between Healthy and unhealthy plants, a difference not always clearly Visible to the human eye. Thus, these views can assist in Assessing crop growth and production. Crops can be surveyed at any time using agricultural drones, allowing for Rapid identification of problems.

Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), commonly known as a Drone is an aircraft without any human pilot, crew or Passengers on board. UAVs are a component of an unmanned aircraft system (UAS), which include additionally a ground-based controller and a system of communications With the UAV. [1][2] The flight of UAVs may operate under Remote control by a human operator, as remotely-piloted Aircraft (RPA), or with various degrees of autonomy, such As autopilot assistance, up to fully autonomous aircraft that Have no provision for human intervention .

The term drone has been used from the early days of Aviation, being applied to remotely-flown target aircraft Used for practice firing of a battleship's guns, such as the 1920s Fairey Queen and 1930s de Havilland Queen Bee . Later examples included the Airspeed Queen Wasp and Miles Queen Martinet, before ultimate replacement by the GAF Jindivik . The term remains in common use. That is An Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) is defined as a “powered, aerial vehicle that does not carry a human Operator, uses aerodynamic forces to

provide vehicle lift, Can fly autonomously or be piloted remotely, can be Expendable or recoverable, and can carry a lethal or Nonlethal payload”. UAV is a term that is commonly Applied to military use cases. However missiles with Warheads are not considered UAVs because the vehicle Itself is a munition.

The term unmanned aircraft system (UAS) was adopted by The United States Department of Defense (DoD) and the United States Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) in 2005 According to their Unmanned Aircraft System Roadmap 2005–2030. The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) and the British Civil Aviation Authority adopted this Term, also used in the European Union’s Single-European- Sky (SES) Air-Traffic-Management (ATM) Research (SESAR Joint Undertaking) roadmap for 2020. This term emphasizes the importance of elements other than the Aircraft. It includes elements such as ground control Stations, data links and other support equipment. A similar Term is an unmanned-aircraft vehicle system (UAWS), remotely piloted aerial vehicle (RPAV), remotely piloted Aircraft system (RPAS). Many similar terms are in use.

“Unoccupied” and “uninhabited” are occasionally used as Gender-neutral alternatives to “unmanned”.

In addition to the software, autonomous drones also employ a host of advanced technologies that allow them to carry out their missions without human intervention, such as Cloud computing, computer vision, artificial intelligence Machine learning, deep learning, and thermal sensors.

Under new regulations which came into effect 1 June 2019, The term RPAS (Remotely Piloted Aircraft System) has been Adopted by the Canadian Government to mean “a set of Configurable elements consisting of a remotely piloted Aircraft, its control

station, the command and control links And any other system elements required during flight Operation”.

The relation of UAVs to remote controlled model aircraft is Unclear. UAVs may or may not include Model aircraft. Some jurisdictions base their definition on Size or weight; however, the US FAA defines any unscrewed Flying craft as a UAV regardless of size. For recreational Uses, a drone (as opposed to a UAV) is a model aircraft that has first-person video, autonomous capabilities, or both.

Brief History of Drone

The earliest recorded use of an unmanned aerial vehicle for War fighting occurred in July 1849, serving as a balloon Carrier (the precursor to the aircraft carrier) in the first Offensive use of air power in naval aviation. Austrian forces besieging Venice attempted to launch some 200 incendiary balloons at the besieged city. The balloons were launched mainly from land; however, some were also launched from the Austrian ship SMS Volcano. At least one Bomb fell in the city; however, due to the wind changing after launch, most of the balloons missed their target, and some drifted back over Austrian lines and the launching Ship Volcano.

The Significant development of drones was started in the early 1900s, and originally focused on providing practice targets for training military personnel. The earliest attempt at a Powered UAV was A. M. Low’s “Aerial Target” in 1916. Low confirmed that Geoffrey de Havilland’s monoplane was the one that flew under control on 21 March 1917 using his Radio system. Other British unmanned developments Followed during and after World War I leading to the fleet of Over 400 de Havilland 82 Queen Bee aerial targets that went into service in 1935.

Nikola Tesla described a fleet of uncrewed aerial combat Vehicles in 1915. These developments also inspired the Construction of the Kettering Bug by Charles Kettering from Dayton, Ohio and the Hewitt-Sperry Automatic Airplane. Initially meant as an uncrewed plane, that would carry an Explosive payload to a predetermined target. The first Scaled remote piloted vehicle was developed by film star and model-airplane enthusiast Reginald Denny in 1935.

In World War II Development continued during World War I, when the Dayton-Wright Airplane Company invented a pilotless aerial Torpedo that would explode at a preset time. In 1940 Denny started the Radio plane Company and more models Emerged during World War II – used both to train anti-aircraft Gunners and to fly attack missions. Nazi Germany produced and used various UAV aircraft during the war, like the Argus as 292 and the V-1 flying bomb with a jet engine. After World War II the development continued in vehicles such as The American JB-4 (using television/radio-command Guidance), the Australian GAF Jindivik and Teledyne Ryan Firebee I of 1951, while companies like Beechcraft offered Their Model 1001 for the U.S. Navy in 1955. Nevertheless, they were little more than remote-controlled Airplanes until the Vietnam War.

In Postwar period, in the year 1959, the U.S. Air Force, concerned about losing pilots over hostile territory, began planning for the use of Uncrewed aircraft. Planning intensified after the Soviet Union shot down a U-2 in 1960. Within days, a highly Classified UAV program started under the code name of “Red Wagon”. The August 1964 clash in the Tonkin Gulf Between naval units of the U.S. and North Vietnamese Navy Initiated America’s highly classified UAVs (Ryan Model 147, Ryan AQM-91 Firefly, and Lockheed D-21) into their first combat Missions of the Vietnam War.

When the Chinese Government showed photographs of downed U.S. UAVs via Wide World Photos, the official U.S. response was “no comment”. During the War of Attrition (1967–1970) the first tactical UAVs installed with reconnaissance cameras were first tested by the Israeli intelligence, successfully bringing Photos from across the Suez Canal. This was the first time that tactical UAVs that could be launched and landed on Any short runway (unlike the heavier jet-based UAVs) were Developed and tested in battle.

In the 1973 Yom Kippur War, Israel used UAVs as decoys to spur opposing forces into wasting expensive anti-aircraft Missiles. After the 1973 Yom Kippur war, a few key People from the team that developed this early UAV joined A small startup company that aimed to develop UAVs into a Commercial product, eventually purchased by Tadiran and Leading to the development of the first Israeli UAV. In 1973, the U.S. military officially confirmed that they had been using UAVs in Southeast Asia (Vietnam). Over 5,000 U.S. airmen had been killed and over 1,000 more were missing or captured. The USAF 100th Strategic Reconnaissance Wing flew about 3,435 UAV missions during the war at a cost of about 554 UAVs lost to all Causes. In the words of USAF General George S. Brown, Commander, Air Force Systems Command, in 1972, “The Only reason we need (UAVs) is that we don’t want to needlessly expend the man in the cockpit.” Later that Year, General John C. Meyer , Commander in Chief, Strategic Air Command , stated, “we let the drone do the high-risk Flying ... the loss rate is high, but we are willing to risk more Of them ...they save lives!” During the 1973 Yom Kippur War, Soviet-supplied surface-

To-air missile batteries in Egypt and Syria caused heavy Damage to Israeli fighter jets. As a result, Israel developed The IAI Scout as the first UAV with real-time

Surveillance. The images and radar decoys provided by these UAVs helped Israel to completely neutralize the Syrian air defenses at the start of the 1982 Lebanon War, resulting in no pilots downed. In Israel in 1987, UAVs were first used as proof-of-concept of super-Agility, post-stall controlled flight in combat-flight Simulations that involved tailless, stealth technology-based, Three-dimensional thrust vectoring flight control, and jet-Steering.

Modern UAVs with the maturing and miniaturization of applicable Technologies in the 1980s and 1990s, interest in UAVs grew within the higher echelons of the U.S. military. In the 1990s, The U.S. DoD gave a contract to AAI Corporation along with Israeli company Malat. The U.S. Navy bought the AAI Pioneer UAV that AAI and Malat developed jointly. Many of These UAVs saw service in the 1991 Gulf War. UAVs demonstrated the possibility of cheaper, more capable Fighting machines, deployable without risk to aircrews. Initial generations primarily involved surveillance aircraft, But some carried armaments, such as the General Atomics MQ-1 Predator , that launched AGM-114 Hellfire air-to-Ground missiles. The Central Intelligence Agency also operated UAVs by 2013 at least 50 Countries used UAVs such as China, Iran, Israel, Pakistan, Turkey, and others designed and built their own varieties. The use of drones has continued to increase. Due to Their wide proliferation, no comprehensive list of UAV Systems exists. The development of smart technologies and improved Electrical power systems led to a parallel increase in the Use of drones for consumer and general aviation activities.

As of 2021, quad copter drones exemplify the widespread Popularity of hobby radio-controlled aircraft and toys, However the use of UAVs in commercial and general Aviation is limited by a lack of

autonomy and new regulatory Environments which require line-of-sight contact with the Pilot.

In 2020 a Kargu 2 drone hunted down and attacked a Human target in Libya, according to a report from the UN Security Council's Panel of Experts on Libya, published in March 2021. This may have been the first time an Autonomous killer robot armed with lethal weaponry Attacked human beings.

Application

In recent years, autonomous drones have begun to transform various application areas as they can fly beyond Visual line of sight (BVLOS) while maximizing Production, reducing costs and risks, ensuring site safety, Security and regulatory compliance, and by protecting the Human workforce in times of a pandemic. They can also be used for consumer-related missions like package Delivery, as demonstrated by Amazon Prime Air, and critical Deliveries of health supplies. There are numerous civilians, commercial, military, and aerospace applications for UAVs. These include:

General Recreation, Disaster relief , archeology , conservation of Biodiversity and habitat , law enforcement , crime , and Terrorism.

Commercial

Aerial surveillance, filmmaking, journalism, scientific Research, surveying, cargo transport, mining, Manufacturing, Forestry, solar farming, thermal energy, Ports and agriculture. Unmanned combat aerial vehicle with extensive cost reductions and advancements in the UAVs technology, the defense forces around the globe are increasingly using these for various applications such as Surveillance, logistics, communication, attack and Combat As of 2020, seventeen countries have

armed UAVs, and More than 100 countries use UAVs in a military Capacity. The global military UAV market is dominated By companies based in the United States, China, and Israel. By sale numbers, The US held over 60% military- Market share in 2017. Four of top five military UAV Manufactures are American including General Atomics, Lockheed Martin , Northrop Grumman and Boeing , followed By the Chinese company CASC .[China has established And expanded its presence in military UAV market since 2010. Of the 18 countries that are known to have received Military drones between 2010 to 2019, the top 12 all purchased their drones from China. Israel companies Mainly focus on small surveillance UAV system and by Quantity of drones, Israel exported 60.7% (2014) of UAV on The market while the United States export 23.9% (2014); top Importers of military UAV are The United Kingdom (33.9%) and India (13.2%). United States alone operated over 9,000 Military UAVs in 2014. General Atomics is the Dominant manufacturer with the Global Hawk and Predator/Mariner systems product-line. For intelligence and reconnaissance missions, the inherent Stealth of micro UAV flapping-wing ornithopters , imitating Birds or insects, offers potential for covert surveillance and Makes them difficult targets to bring down. Reconnaissance, attack, demining , and target practice.

The Civilian

The civilian (commercial and general) drone market is dominated by Chinese companies. Chinese drone Manufacturer DJI alone had 74% of the civil market share in 2018, with no other company accounting for more than 5%, and with \$11 billion forecast global sales in 2020. Following increased scrutiny of its activities, the US Interior Department grounded its fleet of DJI drones in 2020, while The Justice Department

prohibited the use of federal funds for the purchase of DJI and other foreign made UAVs. DJI is followed by Chinese company Yuneec, US Company 3D Robotics and French company Parrot with a significant gap in market share.

As of May 2021, 873,576 UAVs have been registered with the US FAA, of which 42% are categorized as commercial drones and 58% As recreational drones. 2018 NPD point to consumers increasingly purchasing drones with more advanced Features with 33 percent growth in both the \$500+ and \$1000+ market segments.

The civil UAV market is relatively new compared to the Military one. Companies are emerging in both developed And developing nations at the same time. Many early stage Startups have received support and funding from investors.

Aerial photography

Drones or UAV can also be suited for capturing aerial shots in Photography and cinematography, and are widely used for this purpose. Small drones avoid the need for precise Coordination between pilot and cameraman, with the same Person taking on both roles. However, big drones with Professional cine cameras, there is usually a drone pilot And a camera operator who controls camera angle and Lens. For example, the AERIGON cinema drone which is used in film production in big blockbuster movies is Operated by 2 people. As global demand for food production grows exponentially, Resources are depleted, farmland is reduced, and Agricultural labor is increasingly in short supply, there is an Urgent need for more convenient and smarter agricultural Solutions than traditional methods, and the agricultural Drone and robotics industry is expected to make Progress. The Agricultural drones have been used in areas like Nigeria in other to help and

build sustainable agriculture. The use of UAVs is also being investigated to help detect and fight wildfires, whether through observation or launching pyrotechnic devices to start backfires.

Effectiveness of Drones in The Agricultural Sector

For years, humans have been experimenting with unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to determine their applications apart from its military use. However, the rapid development of the consumer (mainly hobbyists) and professional drone market in the past few years can be credited to miniaturization of the device, development of long lasting batteries that allow drones to be flown for hours and cover larger distances, and the ability of different sensors to be added such as cameras for imagery purposes and remote communications. Indeed, the global drones in 2016 were \$8.5 billion, and it is estimated that by 2021, expected sales will reach \$12 billion.

The application of the drones in different industrial sectors has also increased the popularity of the drones in the recent past, such as in the transport, security, and infrastructure also in the agricultural industry (Mammì & Rossi, 2017). Majority of the proponents of the drones have made the argument that the use of drones will ensure faster and more precise results than the use of the traditional processes and methods, which rely on large human workforce. The use of drones is also expected to reduce the overall cost of farming and compliance related costs and improve safety levels when conducting different agricultural practices.

Drones in The Agricultural Industry

Historically, one of the most effective ways that farmers have used or applied to meet and overcome the constant changes and challenges that couple this sector and meet

the growing food demands has been adopting new technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (Meivel, Dinakaran, Gandhiraj, & Srinivasan, 2016). The application of these technologies has resulted in the enhancement of new, and at times, existing farming practices and tools that have already been deployed on the farms. For instance, the use of connected tractors is one of the most popular new technologies that are currently being used in the farming sector to improve yields.

Brief History of Agriculture Drone

Agricultural Drones are currently considered a relatively recent and even less mature tool in relation to the new technologies that are currently being used, or applied in smart or precision agriculture. Currently, there are two types of drones that are used in the agricultural sector:

1. Medium sized (which are mainly used for the analysis applications)
2. Larger drones (which are used for planting and spraying of pesticides in the field).

The first UAS in the agricultural sector were developed in the 1980s for crop dusting purposes. Over the years, the advancement of technology in the agricultural sector has mainly been in the following areas: the precise aerial application of pesticides and fertilizers over the agricultural areas and aerial imaging to support both crop field mapping and growth monitoring. A majority of the agricultural UAS are Micro Air Vehicles (MAVs), fixed-wing or rotary-winged helicopters that are considered to be of low cost, low speed, low ceiling altitude, light weight, and they have a low payload weight with short endurance period. As a majority of the farming applications require only low-medium

endurance capability, a majority of the UAS are gasoline or methanol-fueled or are electric-powered and therefore use rechargeable batteries or solar power. It is important to point out that even though the UAS (which use rechargeable batteries) are mainly for short endurance runs whereas solar powered UAS can last for a longer endurance period. For instance, the UAS that has been fitted with pesticide spraying has a higher payload weight requirement, and therefore, they are able to support longer flight endurance. The less researched area in the agricultural applications of the UAS is the aerial application of water, fertilizer, and pesticides for small-scale farmers. The application of water, fertilizers, and pesticides is crucial for farmers who want to increase their crop yields. While the aerial application method has been proven to be effective for large scale farmers, it can be an ineffective and cumbersome application method in small scale production systems that are common in a majority of the developing countries such as African countries.

However, it is important to point out that the advantages of the UAS over existing technologies is based on their maneuverability, low operation costs, safety, and accuracy.

In 1983, Japan was the first country to attempt to use drones for the aerial application of fertilizers with its development of the Remote-Controlled Aerial Spraying System (RCASS) by Yamaha Motor Corporation. It contributed to Japan's rice, soybean, and wheat crops to increase their yields as they could use drones effectively to control pests that could have affected their overall production. In 1990, Yamaha developed the R50UAS helicopter, which had a payload capacity of 44lb. Subsequently in 1997, the R-MAX (unmanned helicopter) was developed, and by 2000, it had been

equipped with an azimuth and Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS) sensor system.

Currently, in Japan, 90 percent of the crop protection is achieved through the use of drones which have facilitated pest control in the country. The case of Japan farms proves that drones can effectively be used for pesticide spraying and fertilizer application for a majority of the farms in African countries. The reason for this is that the two regions have a comparable farm size per farmer. In Japan, the average farm size is 3.7 acres, while in Africa, it is 2 acres.

The aerial application of water, fertilizers, and pesticides is seen to be highly beneficial in farms that have narrow rows of crops and a relatively hilly terrain as these can be obstacles for tractors.

The UAS can be used for aerial spraying in insect infested areas particularly in the eradication of mosquitoes and tsetse flies in a region. Huang et al. (2009) developed a spray system that fully utilized the autonomous UAS. Their research proved that a spray system can be successfully placed on a UAS, leading to pest management and vector control.

Assessing of Farms Crop

The use of the traditional methods to monitor farming fields requires a lot of manpower and time to successfully complete. However, the use of drones for this purpose means that a farmer is able to fly the device over the farm, take stock, inspect if there are any slow-growing plants that may need additional nitrogen, or supply water to improve their growth. These drones are fitted with sensors that are able to measure specific wavelengths of light that is absorbed and reflected by plants, which leads to the generation of color contrasted images that highlight the problem areas in a crop field.

The images that are generated from the data the drones collect include normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) maps, which were previously created through the use of satellites and airplanes through calculating the ratio of the difference of the near-infrared and visible light radiation.

A combination of the sensor tool and GPS allows the images and videos that were taken in the field to be in a single layer, which can then be analyzed and geo-referenced. It is important to point out that only when the images are in this format can a farmer use a GPS-enabled smartphone or any other device to walk to the identified location, inspect the problem area, and come up with an appropriate solution. As has been pointed out before, sensors are able to capture images that provide crucial information to the farmers. For instance, they can inform the farmer about the health of a plant as they absorb light for photosynthesis purposes. However, there are wavelengths of light that are reflected such as the near infrared (NIR) photons because they do not have enough energy to facilitate the photosynthesis process but have lots of heat. Plants normally reflect the NIR light; however, the ability or mechanism of reflection of light by a plant's leaves normally breaks down as the leaves die. Therefore, the near **Infrared sensors** are designed in such a way that they are able to monitor the difference in the NIR reflectance and visible reflectance, through a calculation known as normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). A strong NDVI is indicative of a high density of plants in an area while weak NDVI can be interpreted as identification of problem areas on a crop field. Fig. 1 shows the difference between a healthy and dead leaf using its reflected light.

8283

As has been pointed out, an NDVI report can help farmers to distinguish the area of the field where crops are growing well and where they are not. A farmer can then create zones in the farm whereby different amounts of fertilizer will be applied, depending on the needs or requirements of the field. In addition to that, as plants react to stress, an NDVI image can reveal to the farmer if there are presence of pests, weeds, and/or water damage that is leading to crops failing to grow as they should. The farmer is provided with necessary information that will help him or her, to identify problems in the farm and come up with cost-effective solutions. There are two approaches that farmers can use when selecting an NDVI camera to capture the images of a farm. The first approach is using an expensive, purpose-built camera with the capability of capturing precise wavelengths. Its added value is that it is able to capture narrow-based frequencies which can provide a farmer with better information on his or her farm health. However, this type of camera is considered to be only useful in specific cases and its effectiveness does not match its high price. On the other hand, a farmer can convert a high-quality consumer camera which can then be fitted on a drone for agricultural imaging purposes. The use of these two approaches will contribute to the delivery of high quality NDVI data for the farmers which they can use to assess the overall health of their farm. Another approach that farmers can use in the assessment of their crops is through remote sensing, which can detect the differences in crop growth and the condition of the soil through variations in the spectral responses. The information that a farmer gets from remote sensing can assist in the identification of nutrient deficiencies, diseases, water status, weeds, damages, and plant populations. Remote sensing (RS) can also be used to detect changes in a pest attack or

disease infested plant before they become visible to the human eye. The following are the **attributes, or benefits** of using RS for data collection purposes of farming information: a non-disruptive method, a systematic manner of data collection, accuracy, and efficiency. These benefits of using the RS will lead to an increase in crop yields and also help the farmers to be in a position whereby they can meet the growing demands of food supply globally.

The UAS have a variety of advantages over the other existing technologies when it comes to providing farmers with information in relation to their crops or livestock health. For instance, unlike the case for satellites, they allow for independent timing of the aerial passes, and therefore, a farmer tends to avoid the inadequate frequency of the satellite surveys, or disturbances that are brought about by cloud cover conditions they are also able to provide ultrahigh resolution to the degree of centimeters. They are also safer to operate in lower altitudes, especially under extreme weather. They have a lower operational cost in comparison to manned aircraft and have higher time flexibility. This is evident in remote areas where there are few manned aircraft, and they are also affordable in comparison to purchasing or hiring manned aircraft for different farming applications.

Monitoring Crops Nutrient

One of the major economic activities in farming is the application of fertilizers such as nitrogen, potash, phosphate as well as micronutrients such as sulphur and magnesium. In a majority of the farms, application of fertilizers is conducted by on-ground equipment such as tractor powered sprayers and pressurized irrigation systems, whereas in large farms with higher revenue they use manned aircraft to facilitate this activity. When

using manned aircraft, farmers mainly use a single application rate for all the areas of the fields that are being sprayed which affects the precision of the fertilizers that are inputted in a farm. In addition to that, the changing wind speed and direction conditions as well as change in elevation of the aircraft during the process of fertilizer application makes precise application to be a nearly impossible activity. The ground equipment application is mainly used to stabilize the crop nutrient status during the irrigation season.

The researchers provide evidence from the World Health Organization whereby, it is estimated that there are 3 million cases of pesticide poisons that occur every year and there are 220,000 deaths that are reported annually, mainly in the developing countries due to the wrong application of fertilizers by farmers in their farming fields. The researchers note that drones can be equipped with an automatic spraying mechanism, which ensures that farmers avoid the harmful effects of fertilizers by ensuring that the right quantity of fertilizer is applied in different parts of the farmland. In another study by Meivel, Dinakaran, Gandhiraj and Srinivasan (2016), the researchers investigated how Agricultural drone (UAV), fitted with a fertilizer and pesticide spraying system, can be applied in precision agriculture. They pointed out that the Agricultural drone that has been fitted with a spraying module does not only lead to precision agriculture, but allows farmers to reach, or access and apply pesticide and fertilizer content in areas that are not easily accessible by the farmers.

Preventing and Monitoring for Livestock in The Farm

Most of the cattle ranchers who have lots of acres or land are using drones as an effective way to keep track of their livestock and conduct surveys of different parts of

their farms where the fences require fixing. In addition to that, they are fitting their drones with high-definition thermal imagers and night-capable cameras to survey if there are unwanted animals in their farms that are preying on their livestock. In addition to that, there are ranchers who are using this technology to survey the quality of their pastures. During pasture surveying, the aerial images that are provided by the drones helps ranchers to map the vegetation health, height, and to monitor weather damages as well as areas that require irrigation on the property. The drones are also used for herding and directing cattle that are on different parts of the farm to a desired location. The drones in the cattle ranches can also be used to check or assess the condition of the water troughs and the gates in the remote locations of a farm. In case there is a water trough that is not functioning, the farmer will not only be aware of it, but he or she will be able to go to its location and fix it. A farmer who is aware of the location of his or her cattle in a big ranch will know where to go and gather cattle that require treatment as well as separate the calving cattle from the rest of the herd and the ones that need to be transported for slaughtering purposes.

The use of this new technology for herding purposes has the potential of introducing active tags to the cattle, which will be instrumental for the ranchers in terms of helping them acquire information at a quicker pace than was the case when using passive Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) tags. The reason for this is that, in the passive RFID tags, a farmer has to be within one or two meters from the animal to read, however, when using active RFID tags, a farmer can be able to read and acquire information of the animal from a distance. This means that instead of a farmer having to scan the whole pasture to know the location and condition of an individual animal, he or she will just use a drone high

enough so that it can spot the herd, and use RFID sensors to read the tags of the animal of interest.

Identifying Diseases

For a farmer to be able to harvest the highest possible yield, it is essential to regularly assess the crop health and try to spot bacterial or fungal infection in the plants. In the past, farmers had to go to their farms and physically assess the condition of their plants, which can be physically tasking and time-consuming for the farmer. However, today, the application of the drone technology means that farmers are able to cover a large piece of land at a short time without the need to physically travel and assess the condition of the plants.

The use of drones to monitor for diseases has been tested in different parts of the world with considerable success. For instance, in Sri Lanka, the eBee drone has been used by farmers to warn them about their plants that have been infested by diseases or pest 10 days before they can see them with their 'naked' eyes. According to Salman Siddiqui, who is the head of IWMI GIS remote sensing and data unit, through the use of near-infrared, a farmer can be able to identify the stress in the plants 10 days before it becomes visible to the eye through capturing the photosynthetic activity images.

The 10-day warning can help farmers reduce or prevent large-scale crop losses. In addition to that, other farmers in a region where it has been affected by certain diseases or pests can be informed, and therefore take adequate measures to prevent the spreading of the diseases and pests which will have a positive impact on a region's overall yield production. In the developing countries such as Kenya, the UN's Food and Agriculture Organization is researching on ways the data collected from drones can help them to provide training and education sessions to the farmers on how to deal with

diseases that affect them. In particular, the foot and mouth disease (FMD) has been proven to be a problem that affects small dairy farmers and research programs are currently being conducted on how drones can be used to reduce the negative impact of the disease on these farmers. For instance, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) trial in Kenya uses the Huginn X1 drone and the researchers found out that in most cases the drones are able to complete their survey on the livestock distribution in a region, provide data to the veterinary personnel who are able to access the affected regions, and provide treatment to the sick animals. In Other countries, drones are being used to identify and kill high-flying pathogens even before they land on the plants. In this case, drones are currently being used to capture the airborne spores of pathogens such as *Fusarium graminearum* that affects wheat and corn before they reach these fields. In addition to that, for farmers who are aware of an impending pathogen outbreak in a nearby area, they are able to conduct air samples and then prepare themselves against the impending attack. In addition, government agencies are conducting large scale surveys in the vulnerable areas and helping farmers to be prepared before an outbreak occurs.

As it was discussed that, the use of drones can assist a farmer in identifying that the plants are diseased 10 days before the disease is noticeable by the human eye. In addition, the use of images from the drones helps farmers assess whether or not their plants have been attacked by pests, fungi, and/or weeds. An important feature to take note when using drones is their ability to easily adjust their altitudes and use different flight paths in accordance to the surrounding topography and geography, which is achieved by additional equipment that is fitted to the drones such as radar and LiDAR, a

light detection and ranging system. They have made it possible for drones to be highly effective for crop spraying purposes. In addition to covering farming areas at a faster period, than when using manual labor, these devices have the ability to scan the ground and apply the liquid pesticides with great precision. There is the argument that crop spraying using drones is estimated to be five times faster than the use of regular machinery. The fig. below illustrates how drones are effective in crop spraying.

Fig. 2: is an illustration of a drone spraying crops in a region of the farm where tractors and even human sprayers may fail to reach because of the crop density

Watching Over Water

Majorities of the farming fields are not uniformly flat and, therefore, even though a farmer may be watering the field, there are some sections that may dry out faster than others or in some cases get missed by watering equipment. This can easily be identified by a farmer who is using a drone which is fitted with the right sensors. The reason for this is that both the spectral and thermal imaging may help the farmer to identify the dry spots whereby the crops will either have low yields, or at times may wither. The imaging process can also assist a farmer to detect if there are leaks in the equipment and the irrigation canals. Farmers can additionally assess the topography of their farming land through the use of

airborne laser scanning technologies, or imaging software, and develop 3D maps. Such maps can be crucial during the farming process as the farmers identify the water catchment areas, help in the identification of the water-flowing direction in the plants, and other land features that influence both the health of the crops and even provide the farmer with information on whether soil erosion occurs or not.

Agriculture accounts for approximately 70% of the water that is used globally, and it is more than twice the amount which is consumed in the manufacturing and industrial sector. With the growing scarcity of this precious commodity, and given its importance in growth and sustainability of the crops, farmers have for years wasted water during the irrigation process. This has been achieved by leaky irrigation systems and wasteful field application techniques. The use of drones in the irrigation process can help to ensure that water is used effectively in the farming lands and also in the identification of areas that are contributing to the wastage of water in the farming fields.

The use of these drones will allow farmers to conduct the vegetation index by calculating or determine the density and health of the crop that is being calculated, all while the crop is still growing. This provides the farmer with the right information, which will lead, or contribute to better crop management.

Soil Moisture and Evapotranspiration of An Agricultural Land

Effective use of water in the farm is one of the most cost-effective measures that farmers want to improve because of the increasing scarcity of water. Therefore, from an irrigation management perspective, there are two factors that a farmer needs to take into consideration to estimate a farm's watering or irrigation needs:

- Evapotranspiration (ET) and
- Soil moisture (SM).
- ✓ Evapotranspiration is defined as the amount of water that a crop uses which is based on the amount of water that is available at the root zone, the type of plant in consideration, weather and seasonal conditions.
- ✓ soil moisture is defined as the amount of water that is retained at the root zone and it varies in different farms depending on the soil type, organic matter, and depth.

These two factors or components can be used to estimate the irrigation needs of a farm through a process known as water balance accounting. Estimation of ET using a drone requires it to be fitted with both Red and NIR spectral filters and a temperature camera sensor. The farmer will also be expected to have the local weather station information to be able to interpret the data that he or she gets from the help of drones. The information that is presented by the farmer from the drones can then be inputted in the irrigation valve zones, which the irrigation technology supports in a specific farm. Currently, soil moisture estimation using drones is an area that is currently still under investigation.

Aerial Planting

As the agricultural technology advances, in the near future, farmers may plant their crops using the drone-planting systems. If this is achieved, it will significantly reduce the labor costs as farmers will be able to use compressed air in the drones to fire seed pods directly into the farming area. There has been much research done within the last couple of years on automated drones for agricultural. Most of these studies focus on crop spearing or surveying, but there are not many studies on

drones that can detect birds with artificial intelligent (AI). One of these drones that is commercialized and found in the market is ProHawk. ProHawk is a drone that is designed to scare the birds away with sound system that emits predator sounds that is equipped with sonic bird repeller. The way it works is simply to fly the drone around the farm or the area you targeting to scare the birds away, once the drone is above the area you want it to be, turn on the sound system to have the desired effect. ProHawk is an effective bird pest control device especially when the flight path is set so the drone can fly with the intended pattern. ProHawk flight time is 15–20 minutes depending on the weather condition and the battery use , not to mention the drone range which is one-mile radius with speed of 30 miles per hour. Drone specification gives the user more than enough time to scare the birds and fly back to the landing zone. The ProHawk drone has been proven to be affective at scaring pestering birds but does not have a coding system (AI) that locks down to follow the birds to chase them away.

Law Enforcement Device

Use of UAVs in law enforcement Police can use drones for applications such as search and rescue and traffic monitoring. Safety and security For examples

US Department of Agriculture poster Warning about the risks of flying UAVs Near wildfires Threats Nuisance UAVs can threaten airspace security in numerous ways, Including unintentional collisions or other interference with Other aircraft, deliberate attacks or by distracting pilots or Flight controllers. The first incident of a drone-airplane Collision occurred in mid-October 2017 in Quebec City, Canada. The first recorded instance of a drone Collision with a hot air balloon occurred on 10 August 2018 In Driggs, Idaho, and United States.

Countermeasures

Counter unmanned air system Italian Army soldiers of the 17th Anti-aircraft Artillery Regiment “Sforzesca” with a portable CPM-Drone Jammer in Rome Further information: electronic warfare The malicious use of UAVs has led to the development of Counter unmanned air system (C-UAS) echnologies such as The Aaronia AARTOS which have been installed on major International airports. Anti-aircraft Missile Systems. Such as the Iron Dome is also being an enhanced With C-UAS technology.

UAVs can also be seamlessly integrated with existing farm management Information systems (FMIS), to reduce time spent planning and in the field. Helping to streamline workflows further, Partnerships between hardware and software manufacturers Can also support agricultural professionals with the Processing and analysis following data collection – all in One system. This allows agricultural professionals to fly the drone and Process the images using accompanying software, before exporting the data directly to an application map for use on Farming equipment, such as sprayers. These measures Enable precision application and ensure less wastage of Materials, which can help save costs. Linking the farmer, Drone maker, software, ag service provider, and agronomist Together, this level of seamless integration enables a Complete drone to tractor workflow – leading the way in Intelligent agriculture and optimizing farm management Methods. This is helping agriculture become a data-Driven industry. Technology giant, Microsoft, is leading the Way in this area with its Microsoft Azure Farm Beats Program, using data analytics from UAVs to boost farm Productivity and reduce resource usage. The future for drone technology in improving sustainability is Promising. The next step will be the use of artificial

Intelligence (AI) to automatically analyze the resulting data. Not only would this encourage more efficient operations but enabling more frequent health assessments would also help Improve sustainability throughout the industry.

Block Diagram

Figure 3 drone block diagram

Circuit Diagram

Fig. 4 drone schematic diagram

Descriptive Working Principle of The Agricultural Drone

Drone Motor

Drones have two clockwise motors and two counter clockwise motors to equalize the turning force produced by the rotating propellers. This is because of Newton's Third Law which states that for every action there is an

equal and opposite reaction. So having an equal number of motors counteracting each other provides stability through equalizing the turning force. This is why on helicopters there is a tail rotor to counteract the turning force from the single main rotor.

Drone Propellers

As drones have two counter clockwise motors and clockwise motors, it also has two different propellers, one for each motor direction. Each propeller rotates pushing the air down on the airfoil surface creating an area of lower pressure on top of the propeller and an area of higher pressure below it resulting in a difference of pressure thus pushing the drone up.

Drone Flight Controller

This is the brain of the drone. The flight controller takes in inputs from the GPS module, compass, obstacle avoidance sensors, and the remote controller and processes it into information that is given out to the ESCs to control the motors. An example of this is seen when a drone is hovering during windy conditions. In the past or if you have a cheap drone it will just drift around as there are no sensors relaying information about the drone's location and how to correct for these changes. In this drone however, the drone knows its exact location from the GPS and the downward vision sensors, so even if wind is blowing it will stay in its exact place this is because the flight controller sends the proper instructions to the ESCs and intern the motors to compensate for the wind factor.

Fig. 5 electrical speed

GPS Module

The global positioning satellite module uses two different global positioning systems to pinpoint the drone's location. It uses the Russian network known as GLONASS (Globalnaya Navigazionnaya Sputnikovaya Sistema) which is comprised of 24 satellites orbiting Earth. This is used in conjunction with the United States network consisting of 31 satellites. These satellites transmit information about its location to Earth's surface. These signals travel at the speed of light and are read by the GPS module on the drone. From there, the drone calculates its geolocation based on the amount of time it took for the signals to arrive from the various satellites. These global positioning satellites give the drone the ability to understand where it is on Earth and maintain its position.

Electronic Speed Controller (ESC)

This is an electronic control board that varies the motor's speed. It also acts as a dynamic brake. The component helps the ground pilot to approximate the height at which the drone is running in. This is attained by gauging the amount of power used by all the motors. Altitude is associated with power drain from the power reservoirs. The ESCs is also connected to the power distribution board (the battery) and the flight controller, as the ESCs

receive signals from the flight controller it changes the amount of power given to each of the motors.

Power Port Module

This monitors the amount of power coming from the battery and distributes it to the drone's ESCs and the flight controller.

Obstacle Avoidance Sensors

This drone has stereo vision sensors on the front and on the bottom, these sensors work in pairs, just like your eyes. These sensors calculate depth by identifying which image pixels from each sensor correspond to the same point. From this, the drone is able to calculate the distance it is from the object in front of it as the distance between the sensors is constant. In other words, the drone solves the Pythagorean Theorem repeatedly to calculate the distance an object is from the drone.

B. Pusher Prop

- The Pusher props are at the back and push the UAV forward hence the name "Pusher props". These contra-rotating props exactly cancel out motor torques during stationary level flight. Opposite pitch gives downdraft. Again, can be made of plastic with the better pusher props made of carbon fiber. You can also purchase guards for the pusher props.

C. Brushless Motors

- Practically all the latest drones use a brushless electric "outrunner" type, which is more efficient, more reliable, and quieter than a brushed motor.

- Motor design is important. More efficient motors save battery life and give the owner more flying time which is what every pilot wants

Figure 6 brushless motor

Axis Gimbal

This is how drone footage is kept so still and stabilized. A motor is placed on the 3 different axes around the camera. When the sensors detect motion on any of these axes, the motors counteract the motion to cancel it. This happens almost instantly as thousands of calculations are executed to provide smooth footage.

Drone Camera A lens opens at the front of the camera and light streams in. An imaging sensor captures the incoming light rays and then processes it into a digital image.

Fig. 7 Drone Gimbal

Drone Battery

These batteries are 'intelligent' meaning that they have over-charge protection, temperature data, charge cycle history, and communicate power output to the drone. This is to ensure the battery is safe to use repeatedly and so that there are no problems during flight.

Drone Antennas

Inside the legs of the drone is the transmission system which relays information from the drone to the controller and from the controller to the drone. Also, in the legs of this drone is two compass sensors which relay its direction to the flight controller.

Downward Ultrasonic Obstacle Avoidance Sensor

One sensor sends out a high-frequency sound pulse and the other sensor receives the pulse. Based on the amount of time between sending the pulse and receiving the pulse the drone calculates the height of the drone off the ground.

Flight LED

These flash various colors to show the user what direction the drone is facing. The two flashing red lights show the front of the drone (the direction the camera is facing). The two green flashing lights are the back of the drone.

Joysticks

These translate the physical movement of the sticks into information that the controller can use to communicate with the drone. The left joystick moves the drone up and

down and does pan right and pan left. The right joystick moves the drone forward and backward and does drift right and drift left.

Main Remote Controller Board

This receives information from the drone about its location, altitude, and what the camera is seeing. It also takes inputs from the joysticks and sends the commands to the flight controller.

Main Camera Board

This processes information from the imaging sensor and gimbal motors to ensure stable footage. This board also processes the camera information and writes the image to the micro SD card.

3.6 SPRAYER KIT OR SPRAYER SYSTEM

The sprayer system consists of a dc pump, tank, controller, nozzles. Sprayer system should be attached to the drone in such a way that the drone is stable even after attachment. When the controller receives the signal from the user end it will turn on/off the pump. In on condition the pump gets turned on and sprays the fertilizers through nozzles. Drone attached with sprayer system is shown in fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Drone attached with sprayer system

Sprayer System Working Principles

The plant protection drone variable spray system comprises a prescription graphic translation subsystem and a variable spraying subsystem. At first, the prescription value of the medication is interpreted by the prescription graphic translation subsystem from the prescription map of the work area. Subsequently, the prescription value is transmitted to the variable spray system. At last, the closed-loop PID control algorithm is utilized to adjust the duty cycle according to the prescription value received. By assigning a value to the single-chip timer counter, a square wave signal with an adjustable duty cycle is generated to adjust the rotation speed of the micro-diaphragm pump. Therefore, the way of variable spraying is realized. In the spray system pipeline, the flow information in the spray pipeline is fed back to the STM32 controller by the Hall flow sensor. Meanwhile, the instantaneous flow rate, real-time position, flight parameters and prescription values are displayed through the liquid crystal display (LCD).

Fig. 9 PMW VARIABLE SPRAY SYSTEM

Fig. 8 shows the Schematic diagram of the structure of a prescription graphical interpretation of a variable spray system. PWM: pulse width modulation. **Note:** 1. Medicine box; 2. micro-diaphragm pump; 3. pressure nozzle; 4. hall flow sensor; 5. liquid crystal display (LCD); 6. buck module; 7. 12 V direct-current (DC) power; 8. drive amplification module; 9. Prescription fig.; 9. GPS.

Variable Spray System Design

The overall structure of the plant protection drone variable spray system is illustrated in Fig. 10 The self-developed subsystems of prescription graphic translation and spray controller were installed in the M23 UAV .

Fig. 10 Physical diagrams of the variable spraying system.

Note: 1. Prescription map interpretation system and spray controller; 2. medicine case; 3. Hall flow sensor; 4. miniature diaphragm pump; 5. pressure nozzle.

NOZZLE

Proposed Design and working principle of Agricultural Drone Nozzle

The fluidic oscillator can also be found in previous studies, and a number of visualization studies have been conducted to find out the flow characteristics of fluid vibrators. In this study, a new nozzle was designed, using the flow characteristics of a fluid vibrator s. A nozzle with a feedback channel generates an oscillating jet flow through the interaction of the feedback block and the chamber with the inner block, without additional external equipment. This oscillation can generate a uniform spraying, compared to a conventional nozzle. When fluid is supplied into the feedback channel, a Coanda effect occurs in which the airflow ejected in close proximity to a wall of the feedback chamber adheres to the wall. The nozzle with a feedback channel uses this effect to generate a cross-flow through the feedback flow path inside the nozzle, thereby causing the fluid to vibrate at the outlet.

Fan-shaped commercial nozzles are generally used in agricultural drones, owing to their wide spray width, but the nozzles provide low uniformity. Fig. 11a shows the expected spraying distributions with the conventional and the feedback channel nozzles. Fig. 11b shows the proposed design for an agricultural drone nozzle that can generate periodic oscillation and improve the spraying uniformity. In general, fluid oscillation effectively occurs when a fluid is discharged into a space filled with the same phase fluid. By contrast, when a fluid is ejected on to a different phase, the oscillation is reduced, and the formation of atomized droplets becomes difficult.

Fig. 11 Expected trajectories of spray for (a) commercial nozzle and (b) developed nozzle.

Nozzle Installation of Variable Spray System

The spray amplitude of the plant protection UAV is related to the installation distance of the nozzle. In order to get the theoretical spray size of the variable spray system designed by the project group, four standard angle sector nozzles (110-015 types, LECHLER Company, Germany) were installed side by side. The spray was gradually sharpened at the edge, and the theoretical spray angle of the nozzle was 110 degrees. The plant protection UAV spray system was dismantled and carried out by spraying with self-designed sprays. According to the basic requirement of the spray nozzle, the installation space of the adjacent sprinkler must be more than 50 cm, and thus a better spraying effect can be obtained when spraying. Therefore, the installation space of the nozzle of the project group was 50 cm. A schematic diagram of the nozzle installation is shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12 A schematic diagram of the nozzle installation.

Schematic diagram of nozzle installation. **ote:** H is the height of the GPS from the top of the crop in m; h is the height of the nozzle from the top of the crop in m; L is the installation distance of the adjacent nozzle in m; d is the spray nozzle of the corresponding height in m; M is the width of the overlap area of the adjacent nozzles in m; K is a certain time, with the distance of the drone flight in m; D is the effective spray width of the drone in m.

Principle of Operation of The Entire System

The subject of **Fluid dynamics** plays a significant role for design and development of aircraft and drones. This subject consists of working principle of aerodynamics of aircrafts. A sufficient amount of upward force is required to lift the vehicle against the gravity which is names Lift. the force created to move the vehicle or body in motion is called thrust. These forces can be studied using laws of fluid flows Flow pattern around the cross-section of aerofoil or propeller is shown below. High fluid pressure at the bottom and low pressure at the top of propeller cause an upward force which is called as lift. This force is responsible for lifting the weight of aero-plane or drone.

The amount of lift force depends on the angle of inclination of aero foil or propeller.

Based on the principle of **conservation of energy in fluid flow** (Bernoulli's principle, the sum of all forms of energy in a fluid is constant along the streamline. When air flows over an aero foil or wing, its velocity increases at the top portion. But the pressure of air decreases. In contrast, the air velocity decreases and pressure increase at the bottom side of blade. The next pressure difference across the aero foil results in an upward force which is called as lift. CFD modeling of flow over an aero foil has been important in many vehicular and aerospace industries.

side with your finger to see which direction it's spinning in. It should be spinning clockwise. If not, make a note. Move down the slider.

Fig. 15 BetaFlight Configurator

Now do the same with motor 2 or 3 – these should be spinning counter clockwise. Typically, it'll be spinning the same way motor 1 was, since they are all wired to the ESC in the same way.

Make a note of which way the motor was spinning, and disconnect BetaFlight Configurator. Now, download the BLHeli Configurator app from the Chrome Webstore, and open it. Click “Read Setup”(Your lipo must be plugged in). where you can update your firmware by clicking “Flash all” at the bottom, and selecting the latest firmware version. The ESC type is usually detected automatically.

Fig. 14

Changing Motor Rotation with Blheli_S

- If the whole soldering and assemble is complete. we just need to check motor rotation to make sure all four of the motors are spinning in the correct direction.
- Plug in your lipo and plug in the board to your computer with a USB cable.
- Go into the Betaflight Configurator, connect, then in the Motors tab, check the warning box for motor testing (make sure props are off).
- Gently bump up the slider for motor 1 until it starts spinning, and feel the bell from the

Fig. 16 Beta firmware screenshot

Now, provided all your motors were spinning in one direction:

- If motor 1 was spinning correctly, then you need to “Reverse” the direction for motors 2 and 3
- If motor 1 was spinning incorrectly, then you need to “Reverse” the direction for motors 1 and 4

That’s it, you’re done! Shrink down your ESC heat shrink, secure them to the arms, and ogle your beautiful creation!

Casing/Packaging

A casing/package refers to an enclosure or housing which contain some material or component and functional case. This is normally to protect the contents of the casing from exposure to. Or damage by: heatwater. Knocks from handling or human interference. It may also conceal the components if they are of an unsightly nature and/or do not normally to be accessed.

Packaging/Casing can be temporary or permanent. A fuse box are sometimes housed into permanent casing, as is pipework that is boxed in for purposes of concealment. Some delivery of a sensitive item to a

construction site are likely to be in temporary casing for protection. For such drones, the outer case is mainly constructed in temporary. Casing can be made from various materials, such as:

- Plastic
- Timber
- Cardboard
- Metal

Fig. 17 Agricultural Drone internal case

Fig. 18 Full case of agricultural drone

TESTING, RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The project constitutes both different types of hardware, components and software for the aims of achieving proper successful operation. In the construction of the system hardware, more focus and examine was given for the purpose of achieving the aims. The software was use to program the basic internals component, with the basic view to achieve logical decision and to be able to control the entire system such the propellers control, ESC motors etc. of the drone.

Testing

According to ANSI/IEEE 1059 standard, Testing can be defined as - A process of analyzing a software item to detect the differences between existing and required conditions (that is defects/errors/bugs) and to evaluate the features of the software item.

Fig. 19 illustration of flied drone

Once everything was deemed functional during the test flight, any vulnerable spots that can interfere with circuit board, electronic speed control, or the flight controller were focused on to fine tune the drone. The circuit board is wide open and that could be hazardous. Water, sand, and high winds can damage the drone circuit board when it is flying or when it is arming before takeoff. This damage can cause the drone to crash or even worse losing control which can lead to a serious injury or property damage.

More testing was conducted using video simulation to see the code output in flying mode while the birds are in air. In addition, another video was used to simulate a bird feeding on the farm surrounded by trees. In figure below the code

system displays three screens locking on a bird using video input as a simulation of the bird in real time. In the first screen, the code displays a live feed in the drone's view point. The second screen is the thresh display and the third screen is the delta frame.

Fig. 20 Shows the code detecting birds using video input.

Fig. 21 A result of Spray test site.

According to the prescription diagram, the prescription values of adjacent units are different. In order to explore the uniformity of droplet deposition in each unit and the droplet deposition at the boundary of adjacent units, the sampling bands such as S1, S2 were shown in Fig. 22, in which the operational units each were set to 10 m × 10 m. Fig. 22 shows only the layout of the sampling points in

the adjacent operational units, and the other units were arranged in the same way. In UAV flying one sortie, the total number of sampling bands was 124. A sampling band was set up in the center of each operation unit, such as S4 and S10. In order to study the change of spray volume at the boundary of the operation unit, the sensitivity of the variable spray system was evaluated. The sampling bands were set on the boundary of the adjacent operation unit and to be 1 m and 2 m away from the boundary line on its both sides, as shown. S1, S7 and S13 were the sampling bands on the boundary line; S5, S6, S8 and S9 were the sampling bands on the left and right sides of the dividing line, respectively. The amount of droplet deposition, the sediment density and the sedimentation uniformity of aviation plant protection operations are important parameters reflecting the quality of spraying.

Fig. 22 Inner sampling bands of adjacent operation units.

Note: S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7, S8, S9, S10, S11, S12, and S13 are the numbers of the collection bands

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